

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ДЛЯ ПОДДЕРЖКИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЛЕКСИКИ**Ерденова С.М.**

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THE USE OF TECHNOLOGY TO SUPPORT VOCABULARY DEVELOPMENT**Yerdenova S.,**

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Ни для кого не секрет, что мы живем в век информации. Сегодня все доступно, каждый может в нужный момент воспользоваться интернетом, каждый может работать с разными гаджетами, например, использование интернет-технологий начинается еще в дошкольном возрасте. Мы идем в ногу с современным быстро меняющимся обществом. Несколько лет назад многие и представить себе не могли, что мы имеем, но сейчас можно с уверенностью сказать, что все это внесет свои коррективы. В частности, необходимо использовать несколько технологий в обучении иностранным языкам в развитии интересов учащихся, словарного запаса. Об этом и пойдет речь в сегодняшней статье. Целью современной системы образования является подготовка инновационной, развитой, конкурентоспособной личности, готовой к участию в общественно-политической жизни Республики Казахстан. Задачами современного образования являются воспитание казахстанского патриотизма, уважения прав и свобод человека, формирование компетентной, активной, творческой личности, готовой к успешной и результативной деятельности. В педагогической практике давно используется термин «активные методы и формы обучения». Она объединяет группу педагогических технологий, позволяющих добиться высокого уровня учебной активности учащихся. В современном образовательно-воспитательном процессе наиболее важным является развитие личности каждого учащегося, необходимость создания педагогических технологий, обеспечивающих его деятельность. Необходимо создать образовательную среду, в которой обучающийся стремится получить новые результаты своей работы и в дальнейшем успешно применять их на практике. Сегодня мы не можем не думать о том, что ждет наших учеников. Известно, что будущее требует от них наличия большой базы знаний не только в выбранной ими профессии, но и в области современных технологий. Сегодня большинство предложений требуют минимальных знаний компьютера, поэтому при подготовке специалистов очень важно учитывать, что современные информационные технологии глубоко проникают в нашу жизнь.

Цель исследования: изучить использование интернет-ресурсов в обучении английскому языку в общеобразовательных учреждениях и важность их использования в технологиях обучения. Формирование современного мировоззрения личности в условиях повышения квалификации и информатизации.

Заключение. В статье описаны современные методы обучения иностранным языкам. В статье содержится материал о преимуществах и перспективах использования описанных технологий в учебном процессе в вузе, которые можно рассматривать как альтернативные средства оценки уровня результатов, достигнутых студентами в учебной деятельности и личностном росте.

ABSTRACT

It's no secret that we live in the information age. Today, everything is available, everyone can use the Internet at the right time, everyone can work with different gadgets, for example, the use of Internet technologies begins in a preschool. We keep pace with today's rapidly changing society. Several years ago, many could not imagine what we have, but now we can say with confidence that all this will make its own adjustments. In particular, it is necessary to use several technologies in teaching foreign languages in the development of students' interests, vocabulary. This is what will be discussed in today's article. The purpose of the modern education system is to prepare an innovative, developed, competitive personality ready to participate in the socio-political life of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The tasks of modern education are the education of Kazakhstani patriotism, respect for human rights and freedoms, the formation of a competent, active, creative personality, ready for successful and effective activity. The term "active methods and forms of teaching" has long been used in pedagogical practice. It unites a group of pedagogical technologies that achieve a high level of educational activity of students. In the modern educational

and educational process, the most important is the development of the personality of each student, the need to create pedagogical technologies that ensure his activity. It is necessary to create an educational environment in which the student strives to obtain new results of his work and successfully apply them in practice in the future. Today we can't help but think about what awaits our students. It is known that the future requires them to have a large knowledge base not only in their chosen profession, but also in the field of modern technologies. Today, most of the proposals require minimal computer knowledge, therefore, when training specialists, it is very important to take into account that modern information technologies penetrate deeply into our lives.

Purpose of the research: to study the use of Internet resources in teaching English in educational institutions and the importance of their use in teaching technologies. Formation of the modern worldview of the individual in the conditions of advanced training and informatization.

Research directions:

- ✓ Research of methods of using several technologies in teaching foreign languages;
- ✓ Identify the types of technologies that develop students' vocabulary;
- ✓ Focus on modern innovative information technologies and ideas in teaching a foreign language in educational institutions

Scientific and practical value. When teaching English, everyone the student must develop his knowledge based on the experience of foreign scientists, using computers in the learning process, working with electronic textbooks, interactive whiteboards, using sites downloaded from the Internet. Therefore, it is very important that the teacher at each lesson, using information and communication technologies, rationally leads the lesson and knows how to organize the educational process.

Research methodology. It is very important to use modern information technologies in teaching a foreign language in educational institutions. Teaching English using information and communication technologies, didactic game technologies and multimedia methods helps to effectively master the language. Therefore, the use of Internet resources and the use of technology to develop vocabulary is a key part of the process of learning a foreign language. Learning using Internet resources is not only a modern form of education, but also a guide to market globalization.

Results of the main analysis. Since the 21st century is the century of informatization, modern technologies are constantly evolving every day. The demands of society, directing the educational process towards innovation, shape its citizens as active, independent decision-makers, multilingual, innovative people, adapted to world skills. As a result, in-depth study of foreign languages in educational institutions continues. New technologies are being developed day after day to enable students to master multilingualism.

Research value. When teaching English, it is important to form the communicative culture of students. The teacher is obliged to develop the creative abilities of each student, to master the practical language, changing the teaching methods, to increase their interest and activity in the learning process. Therefore, in the system of teaching English, it is necessary to regularly use Internet resources, sites, interesting programs, multimedia videos using the language, dialogues. Through computer training programs, students have the opportunity to develop vocabulary, form dialogic and monologue speech, practice grammar skills, learn to read and write fluently, learn vocabulary and pronounce correctly.

Conclusion. The article describes modern methods of teaching foreign languages. The article contains material about the advantages and prospects of using the described technologies in the learning process at the university, which can be considered as alternative means of assessing the level of results achieved by students in their learning activities and personal growth.

Ключевые слова: технология, метод, кейс-технология, веб-квест, процесс обучения, студенты, обучение английскому языку, коммуникативные технологии, дидактические игровые технологии, интернет-ресурсы.

Keywords: technology, method, case technology, web quest, process learning, students, teaching English, communication technologies, didactic game technologies, Internet resources.

*"Technology is art, skill, dexterity, business,
a set of methods, changing the situation"*
V. M. Shepel

Introduction

Educational technologies are the means of achieving subject and subject results, as well as personal results of students. System the work of a teacher to ensure the results of teaching a foreign language must necessarily include the implementation of the following technologies: technology of communicative learning, technology of understanding the communicative meaning of the text, game technology, learning technology in co-operation, design technologies, etc. Internet Resources

in English Language Teaching Technologies is the advantage of using to improve the quality of the language. It is impossible to learn a foreign language without the Internet. The internet is effective in different ways contributes to the solution of didactic tasks:

- Increased interest leads to faster concentration, improves memory performance;
- Cognitive abilities of students are activated. Understanding and the training material will be much more effective and durable;

- Inactive, weak students come to class during the lesson actively participates;
- Using Internet resources in the classroom communication in English will increase. For example, not only teachers, but also students in the class have language resources reproduce and share your thoughts in English. Thus the activity of the English language is increasing.
- Using Internet resources allows students to work independently, teaches to do, improves his research skills in the language, the student learns to independently request information that he wants to know, curiosity, the ability to improve their knowledge increases;
- Conducting lessons through online resources for the teacher irreplaceable value. Teacher diploma in front of students, in front of other colleagues. [1]

The purpose of using the Internet resources is communicative competence and its components in particular information communication, development of digital competencies. Improve grammatical, phonetic, lexical skills, developing students' reading, writing, speaking and listening skills. Currently used digital and multimedia linguodidactic resources: Electronic dictionaries, including in the learning process used: explanatory dictionary, reference book, terminological, illustrated and interactive dictionaries; original materials in the target language (text, graphics, video, audio, game formats); special educational resources for teaching a foreign language (electronic textbooks and printed assignments use of developed computers, programs; interactive educational materials); applications (MS Word, MS PowerPoint, web browsers); electronic synchronous instruments (chats, instant messengers, video conferencing) and asynchronous (email, forums, social groups, networks) communication; internet resources used in the learning process (hot-list, multimedia album, three-character, thematic sample, web-quest) can be used in everyday language learning. [10]

These technologies are used in different ways in teaching a foreign language. Organizational activities of students, for example: classroom work; extracurricular activities; remote learning and blended or blended with audience elements includes training. The most promising training in foreign languages it should be noted that this is with a teacher and students directly via electronic means of communication coordinates related, independent and additional work allows. Multimedia and digital resources for teaching English performs the following functions: Educational (during the presentation of language material used); trainer (teaching skills and used to develop communicative competence); Supervision (formation and control of knowledge and skills); Integrated (the above elements combines. When using multimedia and digital technologies in lesson planning, there are three stages in accordance with the general laws of resource use it is necessary to organize the work by Point before the first text -the Internet resources used here are planned, the task is set in advance. The second stage - text - assignment through digital resources. The third stage after the text is digital resources. The task is automatically checked. [4]

English - all technical tools included, subject with a deep and wide range of possibilities. Foreign language the discovery of multimedia devices in learning, new opportunities. There is nothing surprising in using. Because there is a foreign language in all areas of activity applicable. The leading role in teaching a foreign language is undoubtedly played by multimedia. Methods of play. But first I will look at a simple application includes: multimedia documents that the teacher can compose using Microsoft Word and Demos (PowerPoint) performed. However, their implementation and application is not difficult. Their role in enhancing the lesson and the emotional impact of students very convenient to enlarge. How to use Internet resources for language learning for teachers? It is important to know and learn to use. There are five types of modern English language teaching in the media. Internet resources: favorites, treasure hunt, multimedia scraper ("multimedia album"), thematic sampler, web quest, etc. are widely used in teaching technology. So, for each of the five types of Internet resources consider the structure and methodological content:

1. **Hotlist** ("hot list" - "subject list"). Research topic consists of a list of websites on. Creating a favorites list is great simply. Find a list of information, analyze it and evaluate it. The Hotlist develops students' conversational skills:

- define a topic or problem,
- write down the information read,
- search for information,
- highlight keywords,
- a short and detailed description of the content read,
- the information can be summarized.

2. **Multimedia scrapbook multimedia project** - a set of multimedia materials. it contains links not only to text files, but also to audio video, photo and graphic information. Scrapbook files informative and illustrative when studying a particular topic used as material.

Multimedia scrapbook develops students' skills

- search for information,
- highlight keywords,
- define a topic or problem,
- basic information from the second, or from what you heard, the necessary information you can infer from what you see.

3. **Treasure hunt ("treasure hunt")** - this structure is similar to favorites list and album.

Explored here there are also links to the topic, but each link contains the content of the site, differs in questions about. Questions allow students to focus on exploratory cognition, action. At the end, students are asked to respond to understand the topic.

4. **Object sampler ("object sampler")** - aimed at discussing research topics. Students only not only to search and organize the material, but also express and substantiate their own opinion on the issue under discussion. [8,7]

5. **Web quest (English Web quest - "Internet project")** - the most difficult. Internet resource type. This is one of the four resources mentioned above components and involves the implementation of the project. Project activities using Internet resources are carried

out according to the structure freezes. Audience students are the first to learn data get to know each other, give a specific topic. Then students in groups divided. Each group is asked to go through a specific aspect of the study and then discussed in the group. Students after research and discussion thus reassembled. From each of the main groups to new groups was presented one by one. [12]

In the process of organizing pedagogical support of students in the study of the subject "Foreign language" project activity can also be carried out in the form of a "case" method. Case technologies (training on example of specific cases) are traditionally used in teaching, when trainees are offered specific situations from practice. Teachers who use the case study have different understanding of its essence and it is interpreted as:

- innovative technology in a methodological context: a complex system in which other methods of cognition are integrated;
- the form of organizing students' independent work;
- project;
- the way of organizing the educational material (for example, speaking in a foreign language);
- group type work;
- learning tool professionally oriented communication in English.

Methodists and educators highlight the structure of the case certain components. Thus, A.E. Niyazova believes that each case contains exercises that ensure the activation of the four components allocated in the content of teaching foreign language speaking: motivational, procedural, effective, reflective. Exercise can be represented by three groups: 1) directed to provide students with an educational and speech situation, topic, problem; 2) aimed at preparation of discussions, projects, brainstorming; 3) control character. [5] Case study professionals argue that each case material should have an individual structure peculiar only to it. A well-written case is characterized by clearly defined temporal, plot and outreach structures. Case method in methodological context is complex a system into which other methods of cognition are integrated. According to E. N. Krasikova, in it includes modeling, game methods, brainstorming discussion. T.P. Frolova identifies three main components in the structure of the case: 1) Introduction: problem statement; names and character positions. 2) Problem - a short description (from the perspective of various participant's events). 3) Materials for solution (scientific, methodological, statistical, literary and etc.) [6] It should be noted that the methodology distinguishes three types of case presentation: printed, multimedia case, video case. When working on a case, there are three stages: introductory, research, presentation. M.Y. Eremina describes the technology of work when using case method, which includes three phases: before class, during the time of the lesson, after the lesson, also determines actions of the teacher and students. On the first phase, the teacher: 1) selects the case; 2) Defines materials; 3) develop a script classes; trainee: 1) receives a case and a list recommended literature; 2) independently prepares for the lesson. In the

second phase, the teacher: 1) organizes a preliminary discussion of the case; 2) divides the group into subgroups; 3) leads the discussion of the case in subgroups; the trainee: 1) asks questions that deepen the understanding of the case and the problem; 2) develops solution options; 3) accepts or participates in decision making. In the last phase, the teacher: 1) evaluates the work; 2) evaluates decisions taken; trainee: 1) is written report (draft) on this topic. [3]

O.Y. Pestretsova, referring to the problem of typology of web quests and their characteristics, notes that web quests can cover a separate problem, academic subject, topic, can be interdisciplinary too. The results of the web quest, depending on the studied material can be presented in the form of an oral presentation, essay, etc. The result of this work can be your own multimedia web pages and web sites for a given topic, compiled from materials received in the course of work (texts, photos, graphics, video clips, sound materials). These pages can be posted on the university website. The result works can also be electronic multimedia presentations in Microsoft Power Point or any other who can also be posted on the university website or within the educational network of the university. It is also possible to publish the results printed web quests (brochures, student development) based on materials obtained from The Internet. [11]

Viable forms of working with web-quests appear to be the following:

- Creation of short-term web quests for linguistic and cultural and problematic topics. The result of the work can be discussions, round tables, small presentations.
- Creation of medium and long term web quests that can be completed students partly in class, partly extracurricular, with independent work in computer labs.
- Creation of web quests by the students themselves. This option can be applied to senior courses or master's.

Among the benefits of using web quests identified the following:

- authenticity of text material and increased motivation;
- development of thinking skills;
- atmosphere of cooperation.

Web quest technologies provide in the learning process:

- virtual socio-cultural environment of the country of the target language;
- the authenticity of the materials used, presented on the network;
- motivation of students for independent cognitive activity;
- development of information culture of trainees as a necessary component general cultural competence of a modern personality.

Among other advantages of web quest technologies, it was also possible to establish a creative character. Their implementation; on the one hand, in an atmosphere of cooperation and a sense of responsibility for the success of a common cause, and on the other hand, in the spirit of competition and high motivation for success with real and the tangible fruits of their own

labor. Except this, work with the use of the Internet is carried out by students with great enthusiasm and high motivation. Multimedia content and the hypermedia structure of the Internet, the authenticity of the materials give the student a feeling presence in the linguistic environment and freedom of choice, remove the limitation of the framework of any study guide. Among the clear advantages of using web quests in the educational process, one can single out learning in an atmosphere of cooperation and the responsibility of each student for success implementation of the entire project as a whole (cooperative learning). All of these factors are one of the main reasons for high efficiency work on the technology of web quests. In conclusion, I would like to note that all the listed factors, along with the information wealth and richness of the Internet socio-culturally significant information, as well as the result of completing the quest, which has real value and application in the further educational and professional activities of students, are one of the main reasons for the high efficiency of web quest technology. Due to the fact that modern man is in a continuous process of acquiring knowledge, introducing a web quest into the educational process allows the student to independently organize their teaching, regulate and direct it. The web quest is thus based on a constructivist approach to learning. It allows you to efficiently use Internet resources in the educational process and successfully form motivation and interest in teaching students. The use of the web quest methodology in working with students studying foreign languages contributes to creating students' sustained interest in learning a foreign language and improving speech skills and abilities, familiarization with reading artistic, journalistic and special literature in a foreign language, improving the intellectual abilities of the individual, obtaining aesthetic and cognitive interest, realizing creative potential. [2]

References

1. Beljakov A.V., Matvejchev O.A. Bol'shaja aktual'naja političeskaja jenciklopedija. – M.: Jeksmo, 2009. – 412 s.
2. Vorob'jov G.A. Veb-kvest tehnologij v obuchenii sociokul'turnoj kompetencii: Anglijskij jazyk, lingvisticheskij vuz: Dis. ... kand. ped. nauk, Pjatigorsk, 2004. – 220 s
3. Kudrjavceva L.V. Ispol'zovanie telekommunikacionnyh proektov dlja formirovanija inojazyčnoj

sociokul'turnoj kompetencii u uchashhihsja starshih klassov // Inostr. jazyki v shkole. – 2007. – № 4. – S. 49-53.

4. Krasikova E.N. Kejs-metod v strukture i sodержanii metodicheskoy kompetencii lingvista-prepodavatelja: avtoref. ... dis. kand. ped. nauk. Stavropol', 2009. 24 s.

5. Nijazova A.E. «Kejsovyj metod» v obuchenii inojazychnomu govoreniju uchashhihsja sed'mykh vos'mykh klassov // Metodiki obuchenija inostrannym jazykam v srednej shkole. SPb.: KARO, 2006. – S. 109-150.

6. Mihajlenko T.M. Igrovye tehnologii kak vid pedagogicheskikh tehnologij // Pedagogika: tradicii i innovacii: materialy Mezhdunar. nauch. konf. (g. Cheljabinsk, oktjabr' 2011 g.). – T. I. – Cheljabinsk: Dva komsomol'ca, 2011. – S. 140-146

7. Rudenko-Morgun O.I. Tendencii sovremennoj metodiki prepodavaniya jazyka i novye informacionnye tehnologii // Obshheobrazovatel'nye discipliny i jazyk special'nosti v professional'noj podgotovke nacional'nyh kadrov na nachal'nom jetape obuchenija v vuze: Tez. dokl. Mezhd. nauch.-prakt. konf. 23-24 nojabrja 2000 g. – M.: RUDN, 2000. – S. 239.

8. Rymanova, I. E. Istorija razvitija jelektronnyh tehnologij v prepodavanii inostrannyh jazykov // Molodoj uchenyj. — 2015. — № 11 (91). — S. 1481-1484.

9. Selevko G.K. Sovremennye obrazovatel'nye tehnologii: ucheb. posobie. – M.: Narodnoe obrazovanie, 1998. – 256 s.

10. Protasjenja E.P. Shtemenko Ju.S. Vnedrenie komp'juternykh tehnologij v prepodavanie inostrannyh jazykov // Inostrannye jazyki v shkole. – 1997. – №6. – S. 2-7

11. Pestrecova O.Ju. Ispol'zovanie tehnologii «veb-kvesta» na urokah inostrannogo jazyka // Sovremennye tendencii v obuchenii inostrannym jazykam i mezhkul'turnoj kommunikacii: Materialy Mezhdunarodnoj zaochnoj nauchnoprakticheskoy konferencii (24 marta 2011 g). – Jelektrostal': Novyj gumanitarnyj institut, 2011. – S.284-287

12. Frolova T.P. Kejs-metod kak sredstvo obuchenija studentov-juristov professional'no orientirovannomu obshheniju (na primere anglijskogo jazyka) // Jazyk i mir izuchaemogo jazyka: sb. nauch. ct. – Saratov: TJeU, 2011. – S.180-185.